

Structural, ferroelectric, pyroelectric, and dielectric study of $\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$ ceramics synthesized with precursors obtained by the sol-gel method and doped with lanthanum

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the ferroelectric, pyroelectric, and dielectric properties of La-doped bismuth sodium titanate ceramics ($\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$)_{1-x}La_xTiO₃ (BNLT), using amounts of 0–6.7 at. % La. The precursor powders used to make dense BNLT ceramics were obtained via the sol-gel method using the acetic acid route. All samples were calcined at 700 °C for 1 h and sintered at 1150 °C for 30 min in an encapsulated crucible to avoid Na and Bi volatilization yielding relative densities equal to or higher than 94%. The obtained x-ray diffraction patterns, typical of the perovskite structure, confirm the incorporation of lanthanum into the lattice, which evolved from a rhombohedral phase to a mixture of rhombohedral and cubic structures at higher concentrations. The thermogravimetry and differential scanning calorimetry results indicate that the crystallization of precursor powders of BNT takes place between 500 and 700 °C. In addition, the scanning electron microscopy micrographs reveal a decrease in grain size from 4.5 to 0.5 μm with increasing La content. The ferroelectric hysteresis curves show that the best ferroelectric properties were obtained for BNT 1.3% La, where the obtained values of remnant polarization and coercive field were $P_r = 29 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and $E_c = 39 \text{ kV}/\text{cm}$, respectively. At this concentration, the pyroelectric response shows a higher value, four times higher than the pyroelectric signal of pure BNT.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Lead-based electro-ceramics, such as the piezoelectric transducer, lead zirconate titanate (PZT), are the most-used due to their excellent piezoelectric ($d_{33} = 590\text{--}610 \text{ pC}/\text{N}$) and dielectric ($\epsilon_r = 1700\text{--}1790$) properties.^{1,2} However, considering the high toxicity of lead and its volatility at high temperatures which are required

for the synthesis of lead-based ceramics, there is a trend toward the development of lead-free ferroelectric systems.³ Since its discovery by Smolenskii *et al.* in 1960,⁴ the bismuth sodium titanate (BNT) $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$ perovskite system has emerged as a good candidate to replace lead-based systems due to its high remnant polarization ($P_r = 38 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) and Curie temperature ($T_c = 320 \text{ °C}$).^{5,6} However, it is well-known that BNT is considered a hard ferroelectric due to

its high coercive field values ($E_c \sim 73$ kV/cm),⁷ while it also presents relatively high leakage currents, hindering the polarization process. The leaking current is a characteristic of the system that prevents its use in many applications.^{3,8}

Nevertheless, BNT has been widely studied as a modified system, and using BNT-based solid solutions improves its properties with other systems, such as BaTiO₃ (BT) (from $d_{33} = 83$ pC/N, $k_p = 15.9\%$ for the pure BNT system to $d_{33} = 155$ pC/N, $k_p = 36.7\%$ for 0.4BNT–0.06BT),⁹ SrTiO₃ (ST) (piezoelectric improvement until $d_{33}^* \approx 620$ pC/N for 0.72BNT–0.28ST),¹⁰ K_{0.5}Na_{0.5}TiO₃ (KNN) (piezoelectric improvement until $d_{33} = 94$ pC/N and $k_p \approx 27\%$ for 0.94BNT–0.06KNN),¹¹ and Bi_{0.5}K_{0.5}TiO₃ (BKT) (piezoelectric and dielectric improvement until $d_{33} = 115$ pC/N and $\epsilon_r = 1660$ for 0.82BNT–0.18BKT).¹²

The modification of the BNT system by ion-doping is another method for improving its piezoelectric and ferroelectric properties.¹³ Particularly, the addition of La³⁺ in certain concentrations has led to an improvement in pyroelectric and dielectric properties with systems such as the PZT (maximum energy density improvement from 799.5 J l⁻¹ per cycle for 5/65/35 PLZT to 1014 J l⁻¹ per cycle for 7/65/35 PLZT),¹⁴ BT (from $\epsilon_r = 900$ for undoped BT to $\epsilon_r = 1450$ for 8 at. % La),¹⁵ and BNT (from $\epsilon_r = 350$ for undoped BNT to $\epsilon_r = 928$ for 5 at. % La).¹⁶

Notably, the starting powders used during the synthesis process have a strong influence on the final properties of the ferroelectric systems. The precursor powders can be obtained in different ways: raw powders (oxides and carbonates), by the co-precipitation method, and by the sol–gel method, among others. In particular, the precursor powders derived from the sol–gel method have numerous advantages, such as high compositional homogeneity¹⁷ and great dispersibility.¹⁸ Furthermore, nanosized powders obtained from the sol–gel method significantly decrease the temperatures and times of processing stages of calcination and sintering.¹⁹

In a previous study,²⁰ we explored the BNT system doped with La in a concentration range of 0–6 at. %. However, it was necessary to use an excess of 100% of the Na source in the initial precursors to compensate for the volatilization of Na in the calcination and sintering stages (in order to obtain samples with appropriate ferroelectric characteristics of doped BNT) because we did not use encapsulation in the calcination and sintering processes. In this work, we added encapsulation to the synthesis process, making it possible to obtain samples with high densification and good ferroelectric properties without needing to add excess Na or Bi in the initial precursors.

The aim of this work is to study the effect of lanthanum doping in low-range concentrations (ranging from 0 to 6.7 at. %) on the structural, ferroelectric, pyroelectric, and dielectric behavior of a modified BNT system, obtained using precursor powders derived by the sol–gel method, to avoid the formation of secondary phases.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

We prepared (Bi_{0.5}Na_{0.5})_{1-x}La_xTiO₃ (0, 0.003, 0.007, 0.01, 0.013, 0.033, and 0.067) powders by a sol–gel process. The precursor solution was prepared by dissolution of an appropriate amount of anhydrous sodium acetate (CH₃COONa, 99%, Golden Bell), bismuth (III) acetate [(CH₃COO)₃Bi, 99.99%, Sigma-Aldrich], and lanthanum acetate [(CH₃COO)₃La, 99.99%, Sigma-Aldrich] in glacial

acetic acid (99.7%, Sigma-Aldrich) and deionized water under stirring and heating at 80 °C for 30 min. Second, Ti (IV) isopropoxide [Ti (OCH (CH₃)₂)₄, 97%, Sigma-Aldrich] was dissolved in 2-propanol (99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich) in a ratio of 1:5. Next, a stabilizing agent (acetylacetone, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich) was added in the ratio 1:2 [with respect to Ti (IV) isopropoxide] to the resulting solution, and the mixture was stirred for 15 min to promote a complete reaction. Finally, a stoichiometric amount of the titanium complex solution was added dropwise to the solution of acetate under constant stirring at 80 °C, with a Ti:H₂O molar ratio of 1:5. This process yielded a transparent and stable yellow precursor solution. The BNLT solution was dried in a hot plate at 180 °C for 4 h and calcined in an oven at 700 °C for 1 h to obtain BNT in its corresponding perovskite phase. The calcined powders were ground to obtain fine powders with homogeneous size; they were then uniaxially pressed at 275 MPa for 5 min to obtain pellets with a diameter of 10.14 mm and a thickness of 0.5 mm, followed by sintering at 1150 °C for 30 min using encapsulation to minimize the loss of volatile elements such as bismuth and sodium.

The thermal behavior and decomposition of metalorganic compounds were obtained by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (Mettler Toledo STARTE and Mettler Toledo 822), respectively. The structural characterization of BNLT samples was obtained by x-ray diffraction (XRD) (Rigaku Dmax2100) using Cu K_α radiation. Raman spectra were collected using a Spex-double spectrometer model 1403, using an excitation line at 488.0 nm of an argon-ion laser (Lexel Laser Inc., model 95). The dielectric properties, as a function of temperature, were measured using an impedance analyzer (Agilent 4294A) and a homemade oven with controlled temperature. The ferroelectric hysteresis loop at room temperature was measured using a Precision LC-materials analyzer (Radiant Technology) coupled with a high-voltage amplifier (Trek model 609 × 10⁻⁶). The pyroelectric response was determined via a photothermal experimental setup in which the ceramic sample, with Ag contacts, previously poled, is heated periodically with a diode laser source; the induced AC voltage due to the pyroelectric effect is measured in amplitude and phase with a lock-in amplifier. The pyroelectric response is directly the amplitude of the AC signal as a function of modulation frequency. This signal is proportional to the pyroelectric coefficient (p), while the pyroelectric coefficient is related to the spontaneous polarization (P_s) by the relation $p = (\partial P_s / \partial T)_{E,X}$, where the electric field (E) and stress (X) remain constant.²¹ More details about the measurement method have been previously published.^{22,23}

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. DSC and TG analyses

Figure 1 shows the TG and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) curves of dried xerogel of pure BNT. Exothermic peaks, accompanied by three mass loss steps, are apparent around 98, 311, and 500 °C. However, the DSC curve shows an endothermic peak around 605 °C, which belongs to a solid-state reaction of BNT. There is no weight loss above 650 °C. The weight loss and the exothermic peaks obtained at 98, 311, and 500 °C resulted from the residual solvents and volatile organics. The first-step mass loss of 10.7% in the xerogel is associated with the residual solvents. The second step has a 24.6% mass loss obtained around 200–400 °C, which is related to the

FIG. 1. TGA and DSC curves of BNT xerogel show the temperatures at which the principal transformations occur.

loss of remnant water, acetone, and carbon dioxide.²⁴ Finally, even though the TG curve must not show weight loss during BNT crystallization, it shows a mass loss of 1.2%, which is associated with the volatilization of residual CO₂.

B. Microstructural analyses

The density of the sintered samples, with various atomic concentrations of La (0, 0.003, 0.007, 0.01, 0.013, 0.033, and 0.067), was determined by the Archimedes method. The results presented in Table I show an increase in density up to a concentration of 1.0 at. % of La; density then decreases with higher concentrations, although in all cases, the relative density is equal to or higher than 94%. The shrinkage percentage of the diameter of sintered samples with respect to their diameter before sintering was also determined to be in the range of 10.1%–14.1%.

Figure 2 shows the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs of fractured surfaces of representative samples; the shape is long-round without well-defined faces for pure BNT. This is an important difference between the microstructure of samples obtained with powders obtained by sol–gel and the microstructure of those samples obtained with carbonates and oxides precursors, in which the shape of the grain is generally well-defined. Nevertheless, in the case of precursors obtained by sol–gel, when La-concentration increases, the shapes of the grains are better defined.

Table I shows the evolution of grain size with the concentration of La. The addition of lanthanum to the BNT system leads to a large decrease in grain size from 4.5 μm for undoped BNT to 0.5 μm

for La-doped BNT at 3.3 at. %. We could not estimate grain size for the highest La concentration (6.7 at. %) due to the presence of grain fusions.

A similar effect toward grain size reduction has also been observed in other ferroelectric systems in addition to BNT, such as in the case of BaTiO₃ and the PZT.^{25–27} The effect of La doping on the A sites of the BNT perovskite structure, after substituting Na and Bi, leads to a decrease in grain size; at higher concentrations, it is expected that this substitution also contributes to the appearance of additional phases.^{25–27}

C. X-ray diffraction results

Figure 3 shows the x-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of BNT ceramic samples with various concentrations of La (0 ≤ x ≤ 6.7 at. %) sintered at 1150 °C for 30 min. The sharp peaks in the XRD patterns indicate that the obtained samples had good crystalline quality, free of secondary phases, even in the samples with the highest La concentrations. This result was achieved thanks to the encapsulation stage during the sintering process, without the need to add excess Na to compensate for its volatilization, which is necessary when encapsulation is not included. The crystalline phase identified according to the crystallographic file (ICDD-PDF No. 36-0340) for pure BNT corresponds to the R3c rhombohedral structure.^{9,28,29}

The samples with a low concentration of La (0 ≤ x ≤ 1.3% at) show a good correspondence with the rhombohedral phase. However, for samples with a higher concentration of La (3.3 ≤ x ≤ 6.7 at. %), the diffraction peaks (012) and (110) that are presented in the inset of Fig. 2 show an evolution that allows for identifying the presence of a mixture of crystalline phases of rhombohedral (R3c) and cubic (Pm-3m group) structures.

Previous studies on La-doping into perovskite structures have suggested that La³⁺ preferably replaces A-sites due to their close radii.^{25,27} Shannon³⁰ reported the next ionic radius for Na⁺ (r_{Na} = 1.39 Å, CN = 12), La³⁺ (r_{La} = 1.36 Å, CN = 12), and Bi³⁺ where the latter only shows ionic radii for coordination 8 (r_{Bi} = 1.17 and CN = 8). In coordination XII, Paul Blessington Selvadurai *et al.*²⁹ reported a value of 1.36 Å for Bi, while Liu *et al.* and Yang *et al.*^{31,32} reported values of 1.38 and 1.39 Å, respectively. As can be seen, the ionic radii are very close; considering the oxidation state of La³⁺, the probability that La³⁺ occupies Bi³⁺ sites in the lattice is higher than the probability that it occupies the sites of Na⁺, where a charge imbalance of 2+ is expected. However, the synthesis method intrinsically results in the samples showing a high density of defects in the case of pure BNT (Na, Bi, and O vacancies), for which it is expected that the initial effect of introducing La into the range of low concentrations is the compensation of defects of Na and Bi.

TABLE I. Dependence of contraction, grain size, and relative density in sintered pellets of the BNT system as a function of lanthanum content.

X	0.0	0.003	0.007	0.01	0.013	0.033	0.067
Contraction (%)	12.7	11.2	11.3	13.6	14.1	10.1	11.4
Average grain size (μm)	4.5	3.3	2.0	1.1	0.6	0.5	...
Relative density (%)	94.5	95	95.6	97.0	94	94.5	95.3

FIG. 2. SEM micrographs of the $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})_{1-x}\text{La}_x\text{TiO}_3$ system sintered at $1150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$: (a) pure BNT, (b) with 1.3 at. % La^{3+} , and (c) with 3.3 at. % La^{3+} .

Preferential substitution by Bi^{3+} should manifest; for concentrations greater than 10%, this will lead to Bi-rich phase segregation, as observed in previous work.²⁰ In the evolution of the XRD patterns, a proportional shift in the main diffraction peak is apparent, located in the 2θ region (32.1° – 33.1°) with the La amount added to the BNT system, suggesting a distortion on the lattice. First, there is an increase in the lattice parameter until a La concentration of 1.0 at. %; next, there is a change to a mixture of rhombohedral and cubic structures at higher La concentrations. To describe these changes in lattice parameters, the diffraction patterns of pure BNT and La-doped BNT samples were analyzed by the profile fitting method, using the Fullprof Suite program.³³ Figure 4 shows the Rietveld refinement for a sample of BNT doped with 1.0 at. % La; in this case, the adjustment was realized considering only the rhombohedral phase. X-ray diffraction of sintered samples to undoped BNT and BNT with a low La concentration (≤ 1.3 at. %) were indexed as a single rhombohedral phase belonging to the R3c group. Nevertheless, for higher La concentrations (≥ 3.3 at. %), it was necessary to use (in addition to the rhombohedral phase) a cubic phase for adjustment to the diffraction patterns, indicating coexistence between the rhombohedral phase (R3c group) and the non-ferroelectric cubic phase (Pm-3m group).²⁷

FIG. 3. Comparison of x-ray diffraction patterns for pure BNT and lanthanum-doped BNT. The inset shows the evolution peaks, (012) and (110), with the La content.

Table II shows the adjusted parameters, such as the rhombohedral and cubic lattice parameter (a_R , c_R , a_C), unit-cell volume (Vol_R , Vol_C), phase percentage concentration (% phase), and goodness-of-fit (χ^2), which should be ≤ 1.5 for a good fit.³³ However, high backgrounds of x-ray diffraction patterns for all compositions contributed to higher χ^2 values. As observed in Table II, low La^{3+} concentrations (≤ 1.0 at. %) in the BNT system led to an increase in the unit-cell volume. For a concentration of 1.3 at. % La, there is a slight volume decrease. At higher La concentrations, there are strong structural changes, with the cubic crystalline phase concentration appearing with a 10% at 3.3% La concentration; at 6.7% La concentration, the sample is practically constituted by the cubic phase, with 98.41% of phase concentration.

This particular lattice distortion behavior, also observed in Pr^{3+} -doped BNT and La^{3+} -doped PZT systems,^{26,34} has been related to the generation of micro-strain and cation-vacancies. Both mechanisms may occur when vacancies in A-sites are generated to neutralize the positive charge into a unit cell, and a subsequent distortion in the lattice occurs to stabilize the perovskite structure. As previously indicated, the ionic radii of Na^{1+} , Bi^{3+} , and La^{3+} are similar.

FIG. 4. Rietveld profile fitting of a BNT sample doped with 1.0 at. % La. The profile fitting of the crystalline structure was made considering the rhombohedral structure (R3c group).

TABLE II. Rhombohedral and cubic lattice parameters of $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})_{1-x}\text{La}_x\text{TiO}_3$ ceramics sintered at 1150°C for 30 min, where $x = 0, 0.003, 0.007, 0.01, 0.013, 0.033,$ and 0.067 .

at. % La	Rhombohedral R3c			Cubic Pm-3m		% phase R3c rhombohedral	% phase Pm-3m cubic	R_p	R_{wp}	R_{exp}	χ^2
	a_R (Å)	c_R (Å)	Vol_R (Å ³)	a_c (Å)	Vol_C (Å ³)						
0	5.4899	13.5854	354.599	100	0	10.2	13.3	6.05	2.11
0.3	5.4923	13.6097	355.419	100	0	12.2	15.7	5.91	2.62
0.7	5.4956	13.6126	356.038	100	0	14.5	18.5	8.89	2.03
1	5.5003	13.6094	356.572	100	0	13.3	17.1	9.10	1.84
1.3	5.4981	13.6123	356.367	100	0	11.2	14.3	6.63	2.10
3.3	5.4875	13.5196	352.531	3.9304	60.716	89.59	10.41	11.6	14.6	6.56	2.23
6.7	5.4942	13.4745	350.512	3.8918	58.947	1.57	98.41	12.4	16.4	6.36	2.55

La can enter isovalently by Bi or as a donor by Na with an excess of 2+ electrical charge. At very low concentrations of La, it is expected that, initially, the vacancies of the A site will be compensated; as the concentration of La increases, there will be a competition between substitution for Bi and for Na. The substitution by Na will give rise to Na vacancies to compensate for the electrical charge excess of La. This will lead to a distortion in the lattice, which is observed in this case as a linear increase in cell volume, up to La concentrations near 1.0%. However, a continued increase in La concentrations (≥ 1.3 at. %) decreases the cell volume and induces a change to the cubic structure. Hence, higher La concentrations could eventually lead to an equilibrium into A($\text{Bi}^{3+}/\text{Na}^+$)-site substitution and, therefore, a decrease in the cation-vacancy concentration. In addition, a constant shrinkage of the a and c lattice parameters and the unit-cell volume are related to a continuous evolution toward higher cell symmetry for the BNT system^{27,35} and thus a continuous transition from the rhombohedral to the cubic phase.

D. Raman characterization

Figure 5(a) shows the Raman spectra at room temperature, using an excitation line of an argon-ion laser at 488.0 nm for the set of sintered samples. The spectra of the BNT system shows Raman modes overlapping in four main bands: $A_1\text{TO}_1$ in the range of $109\text{--}187\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is dominated by Bi–O and Na–O vibrations;^{29,36} ETO_2 in the range of $200\text{--}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$, associated with Ti–O vibrations; TO_3 in the range of $450\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, associated with stretching and breathing vibrations of the octahedral TiO_6 ;²⁹ and finally, the LO_3 band in the highest-frequency Raman modes, located at 770 and 830 cm^{-1} , which can be correlated with oxygen vacancies.³⁷ Doping BNT with Cr in site B leads to oxygen vacancies; these oxygen vacancies increase with Cr concentration, generating an increased intensity in the broad Raman band centered around 800 cm^{-1} , showing that the intensity of this band is related to the oxygen vacancy concentration.³⁷

FIG. 5. (a) Raman spectra of $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})_{1-x}\text{La}_x\text{TiO}_3$ sintered samples measured at room temperature, where $x = 0, 0.003, 0.007, 0.01, 0.013, 0.033,$ and 0.067 . (b) Deconvoluted modes obtained by fitting of overlapped A–D bands.

The plot was normalized for the highest-intensity band, corresponding to the second main band. According to XRD results at room temperature, the BNT system belongs to a rhombohedral structure (space group R3c), which is observed until a 1.3% La concentration; with higher La concentrations, the cubic phase appears and increases its phase concentration. Figure 5(b) shows 12 individual Raman modes obtained by deconvoluting the fitted Raman spectra within the measured region ($100\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), using a Gaussian–Lorentzian function. The Raman active phonon modes expected for a rhombohedral R3c phase with A-site disorder (e.g., Bi/Na sites into the BNT system) are a total of 13 ($4A_1 + 9E$), active also in IR.^{29,38–43} On the other hand, the cubic paraelectric phase (Pm-3m) has four optical modes ($3F_{1u} + 1F_{2u}$), where only three modes with F_{1u} symmetry are IR-active and F_{2u} is a silent mode. In principle, these modes are not Raman active modes;^{38,39} nevertheless, distortions in the lattice, impurities, and vacancies can give rise to Raman bands in the cubic phase.

The number of individual modes obtained by the deconvolution process was close to that from the factor-group analysis of the R3c space group. In general, the literature shows a lower number of deconvoluted modes. In our case, the band A_1TO_1 is in the region of $109\text{--}187\text{ cm}^{-1}$, where we found two additional modes. In the rest of the bands, we found the same number of modes reported in the literature;³⁹ this region is associated with vibrations of Bi–O and Na–O. The influence of La on those vibrations, along with the contribution of La–O vibrations, is expected.

Figure 6(a) shows the evolution of the frequency shift of the deconvoluted modes as a function of the doping of La. Figure 6(b) shows the evolution of the full width at half the maximum (FWHM) of the bands of greater intensity obtained from the deconvolution. The greatest changes in frequency shift and in width at half the maximum occur for concentrations of La greater than 1.3%, which corresponds to concentrations at which the cubic phase appears. For higher concentrations, the majority of the modes show a broadening, which can be attributed to the coexistence of the rhombohedral and cubic phases as well as disorder in the A sites due to the random substitution of La in the Bi/Na sites.⁴¹

The changes observed at La concentrations lower than 1.3% are related to local changes within the rhombohedral structure due to

the introduction of La into the A sites of the network. The lower-frequency band, located near 140 cm^{-1} , splits into three individual modes (at about 135 , 151 , and 161 cm^{-1}) in pure BNT. These modes shift to lower frequencies at low La^{3+} concentrations ($\leq 1.3\text{ at. \%}$); when the lanthanum concentration increases to 3.3 at.%, there is a shift to higher frequencies. However, at the highest dopant concentration (6.7 at.%), one individual mode disappears, and the frequencies decrease to about 135 and 152 cm^{-1} ; for the highest La concentration, the XRD results indicate that the crystalline majority phase is cubic. The FWHM of the mode at 135 cm^{-1} shows interesting behavior. First, at low La concentrations, there is a decrease in this parameter. Subsequently, there is a quasi-linear increase with La concentrations of 3.3%; it decreases again with the highest La concentration. The introduction of La with intermediate atomic mass between that of Na and Bi ($m_{\text{Bi}} = 208.98$, $m_{\text{Na}} = 22.99$, and $m_{\text{La}} = 138.91$) into A sites implies distribution vibrations of Na–O, Bi–O, and La–O, which are manifested in this region as a shift to lower frequencies (at lower concentrations). With higher concentrations ($>1.3\%$), the influence of the cubic phase is observed. In principle, Raman bands are not expected in the cubic phase; nevertheless, at La concentrations of 3.3% and 6.7%, a mixture of rhombohedral and cubic phases is yielded. Furthermore, it is common in these perovskite structures that the introduction of dopants such as La into A sites gives rise to a substitutional disorder, breaking the Raman selection rules and showing Raman bands in the same region of the coexistence crystalline phase in this case, the rhombohedral phase.⁴²

The band located around $200\text{--}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ also splits into three modes at 262 , 302 , and 313 cm^{-1} , which survive at higher La concentrations where the principal crystalline phase is cubic. With the introduction of La, all modes show a shift to lower frequencies until a 1.3% La concentration; for higher concentrations ($\geq 3.3\%$), the trend is a shift toward higher frequencies. The FWHM of the 262 cm^{-1} mode shows a slight decrease until a 1.0% La concentration. At 1.3%, the reduction is higher; at higher concentrations, the FWHM shows a linear increase. This region is associated with Ti–O vibrations. The shift to lower frequencies by the introduction of La implies a decrease in the strength of the Ti–O bonds, until a 1.3% La concentration. For higher concentrations, the shift to higher frequencies

FIG. 6. (a) Raman modes frequency shifts; (b) the FWHM of principal deconvoluted bands as a function of La concentration.

implies an increase in the strength of the Ti–O bonds, which is associated with the change to the cubic phase. The overlapping main band around $450\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is split into three components located at 486 , 531 , and 600 cm^{-1} . This region is associated with vibrations of the octahedral TiO_6 , as breathing and stretching modes.⁴³ The introduction of La is expected to induce very weak changes; Fig. 5(a) shows that these modes do not show appreciable changes until a 1.3% La concentration. At higher concentrations, where the shift to the cubic phase is occurring, these modes shift to higher frequencies, which indicates an increase in the strength of bonds in the TiO_6 octahedra. The FWHM of the mode at 531 cm^{-1} decreases monotonically with La concentration until 2% La concentration; at higher concentrations, it begins to increase. This broadening may stem from a distribution of TiO_6 octahedral structures in the rhombohedral and cubic phases under the influence of Bi, Na, and La in the A sites.

Finally, the highest-frequency band consists of three individual modes (at 784 , 810 , and 860 cm^{-1}), which correspond to oxygen vacancies, where an increase in the intensity is related to a higher vacancy concentration. Pure BNT shows these bands due to loss of highly volatile elements such as bismuth oxide.³⁷ However, the intensity of this band diminishes when La is added, especially with large La concentrations ($\geq 3.3\text{ at.}\%$). This behavior indicates that

oxygen vacancies are reduced with the introduction of La. It could be produced for vacancies in Bi^{3+} -sites created during the high-temperature steps, although the introduction of the isovalent La^{3+} ion, in this range of concentration, reduces the generation of oxygen vacancies.

E. Dielectric characterization

Figure 7 shows the temperature dependence of losses and permittivity in samples of the $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})_{1-x}\text{La}_x\text{TiO}_3$ system with varying La concentrations of $x = 0, 0.003, 0.007, 0.01, 0.013, 0.033$, and 0.067 at four different frequencies (1 kHz, 10 kHz, 100 kHz, and 1 MHz). The dielectric function shows small dispersion with frequency. Only two main peaks are apparent within a temperature range of $25\text{--}450^\circ\text{C}$. They are located at around 220 and 350°C for undoped BNT and correlate with a ferroelectric–antiferroelectric phase transition (T_d) and an antiferroelectric–cubic phase transition (T_{max}), respectively.^{9,44}

The value of the dielectric function at T_{max} was around 2665 for pure BNT. Nevertheless, with the introduction of La, the maximum value decreased to 1845 for a 1.3% La concentration; it decreased to 855 for a 6.7% La concentration. At 3.3% concentration, the transition peak from the antiferroelectric to paraelectric phase shows

FIG. 7. Temperature dependence on the dielectric constant and loss at 1 kHz, 10 kHz, 100 kHz, and 1 MHz for pure BNT and BNT samples.

an appreciable broadening. At this concentration, according to the XRD results, there is a mixture of rhombohedral and cubic phases in a ratio of approximately 90:10. At 6.7% La concentration, the dielectric function shows a more uniform value around 760. For this composition, the proportion of crystalline phases is 1.57% rhombohedral and 98.41% cubic phase, and the maxima associated with T_d and T_{max} are much less pronounced. On the other hand, the dielectric function at room temperature fluctuates between 600 and 700, up to a La concentration of 1.3%. At 3.3% concentration, it reaches its maximum around 1000, with little dispersion on the frequency. For the highest La concentration (6.7%), the dispersion with frequency increases slightly, fluctuating around a value close to 710.

T_{max} increases linearly with increasing La-concentration (see Fig. 8), reaching a maximum at 1.3 at. % ($T_{max} \approx 365^\circ\text{C}$); it then drops to lower temperatures with higher concentrations (≥ 3.3 at. %). Furthermore, T_d , known as the depolarization temperature, decreases slightly with La concentration, falling from 220°C for undoped BNT to 207°C for BNT with 1.3 at. %. For the sample with 3.3% La concentration, it was not possible to determine T_d because the peak at T_{max} was very broad and the maximum for T_d was not distinguishable (see Fig. 7).

This temperature shift of T_d toward lower temperatures relates to the increase in ionic radii of lanthanides,⁴⁵ where the lanthanum ionic radius belonging to a coordination number of 12 (CN) has one of the largest radii of all. Therefore, changes in this temperature with the addition of lanthanum are expected. In addition, dielectric curves show a broader shape, which is related to the replacement at A sites (Bi/Na site), which leads to a local heterogeneity in cation distribution, promoting a greater diffuse dielectric behavior.^{9,44,45} At the highest La concentration (6.7 at. %), a large T_d shift toward low temperatures near 71°C is observed (Fig. 8). This may indicate anti-ferroelectric behavior close to room temperature due to the addition of lanthanum.^{44,46,47}

Figure 7 also shows the dependence of dielectric losses on La concentration in the BNT system. The addition of lanthanum in concentrations of 0.3–1.3 at. % leads to a reduction in dielectric losses, compared to the undoped sample. With increasing La

FIG. 8. Dependence of (T_m) temperature, where the dielectric function shows a maximum and ferroelectric-antiferroelectric transition temperature (T_d), as a function of La concentration in the BNT system at 100 Hz.

concentrations, the dielectric losses increase, showing maximum loss for the sample with the highest La concentration, where the donor character of Na substitution by La is manifested. Nevertheless, the losses are always lower than 0.4. Raman results show a reduction in oxygen vacancies with the introduction of La. The reduction in losses at lower La concentrations indicates a reduction in electrical conductivity until a 1.3% La concentration; the hypothesis regarding the reduction in oxygen vacancies is reinforced.^{48,49}

F. Hysteresis loops

The hysteresis loops (P vs E) were measured at room temperature for all compositions. Figure 9(a) clearly shows that the ferroelectric properties of the BNT system were considerably affected by the addition of La. Continuous change in ferroelectric loop behavior from a normal ferroelectric loop (0–1.3 at. % La) to a thin hysteresis loop (≥ 3.3 at. % La) suggests a phase transition from the ferroelectric to non-ferroelectric phase; the hysteresis loop for 6.7 at. % La shows a dielectric behavior. It is known that relatively high concentrations of lanthanum can lead a phase transition from the ferroelectric phase to the pseudocubic phase in the BNT system and BNT-based solutions.^{27,34} Our XRD results show a cubic phase proportion close to 90% for a 6.7 at. % La concentration. However, compositions with small lanthanum quantities show the best ferroelectric characteristics, at around 1.3 at. % La concentration, where we observe the maximum remnant polarization P_r ($28.3 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) and a lower coercive field of E_c (38 kV/cm) than in the pure BNT (51 kV/cm) system. Figure 9(b) shows that, after the maximum remnant polarization at 1.3 at. % La, there follows an appreciable decrease in remnant polarization and in the coercive field at La concentrations greater than 3.3 at. %. The high remnant polarization showed by doped samples with low La concentrations (≤ 1.3 at. % La) may stem from the contribution of La–O bonding, in addition to Na–O and Bi–O bonding, due to the aleatory introduction of La^{3+} into A sites. The compensation of native Bi/Na vacancies is also expected, in addition to the substitution of Bi^{3+} or Na^+ . Since the ionic dielectric polarizability⁵⁰ of Na^+ ($\alpha = 1.8$) is considerably lower than that of La^{3+} ($\alpha = 6.07$), and because the polarizability of Bi^{3+} ($\alpha = 6.04$) is close to that of La^{3+} , an increase in the dipolar moment of the unit cell is expected when Na^{1+} is substituted by La^{3+} (as opposed to Bi^{3+} substitution). The morphological results by SEM micrographs show a reduction in grain size from around $4.5 \mu\text{m}$ for pure BNT to $0.6 \mu\text{m}$ in samples with a 1.3 at. % La concentration. The increase in the polarizability of the unit cell increases remnant polarization. The reduction in grain size and, therefore, an increase in grain boundaries as a function of La concentration can lead to easier domain switching, thereby increasing mobility in the domain wall and making domain switching easier. This reduces the coercive field, facilitating the polarization process caused by relaxation of inner stress generated by electrostriction.⁹ Both effects (increasing the polarizability of the unit cell and reducing grain size) improve ferroelectric behavior, analogous to the “soft” PZT systems doped with donor dopants, in which vacancies at site A are generated to balance the charge of the cell.⁵¹

G. Pyroelectric response

Figure 10 shows the pyroelectric response measurements. For these measurements, samples with a thickness of around $500 \mu\text{m}$

FIG. 9. (a) P–E hysteresis loops at room temperature for BNT and La-doped BNLT samples; (b) Evolution of remnant polarization (P_r) as a function of La concentration at 3.3 Hz and 80 kV/cm.

with Ag contacts were poled with a field of 50 kV/cm for 30 min at room temperature. The poled samples were heated periodically with a modulated diode laser with a constant power of 35 mW. The periodic heating of the sample generated an AC signal due to the pyroelectric effect. The amplitude of the pyroelectric signal was acquired as a function of modulation frequency in the range of 5–40 Hz. The inset of Fig. 10 shows the pyroelectric signal at 10 Hz as a function of the La concentration. The introduction of La increased the pyroelectric signal, with the maximum pyroelectric response obtained for the sample with 1.3 at. % La concentration. Compared to the pure BNT sample, the signal is increased close to four times; at 3.3%, the amplitude signal is reduced to half that of the pure BNT sample, while at 6.7%, the signal is very small. The behavior of the pyroelectric signal based on La concentration is similar to that of remnant polarization with La concentration, indicating the direct relationship

FIG. 10. Signal amplitude of the pyroelectric response as a function of the modulation frequency in the samples doped with La. The inset shows the amplitudes of the pyroelectric signal at a fixed frequency of 10 Hz for various La concentrations.

between these parameters. At a 3.3 at. % La concentration, the remnant polarization shows a drastic reduction. At 6.7%, P_r is close to 0, and a similar drastic reduction is observed in the pyroelectric signal.

Based on our analysis of the results presented in the BNT system doped with La, we make several observations. By synthesizing BNT doped with La (obtained from powders from the drying of a precursor solution of BNT using the acetic acid route as a solvent for the acetates involved) and adding an encapsulation step for the samples during the sintering step, we obtained samples with relative densities higher than 94%. Even for the highest La concentration, we did not observe any segregation of the secondary phase. Thus, it is possible to study the effect of La in modifying the perovskite lattice of BNT, as well as the evolution of its ferroelectric, dielectric, and pyroelectric properties. The introduction of La^{3+} into the A sites where it acts as an isovalent ion in the case of substitution by Bi^{3+} and as a donor when substituting Na^{+1} leads to the creation of vacancies of Na in the latter case. The XRD results show a distortion in the lattice, with an increase in the volume of the lattice until 1.3% La concentration. Concentrations greater than or equal to 3.3% give rise to the structural transition from the rhombohedral phase to the cubic crystalline phase. The SEM micrographs show a reduction in grain size with increasing La concentrations. The improvement in ferroelectric properties with low La concentrations indicates that (in this range of concentrations) La^{3+} initially compensates the inherent vacancies of Bi and Na while increasing its concentration initiates random substitutions of Bi and Na, leading to a distribution of nanoregions rich in Na, Bi, and La that are reflected in the shifts of the characteristic Raman modes of BNT, where the vibrations of the Na–O and La–O bonds and the vibrations of the TiO_6 octahedron are affected.

At La concentrations greater than 1.3%, we observe (in addition to the reduction in the grain size) the coexistence of the rhombohedral and cubic crystalline phases. This cubic phase increases to a proportion of nearly 90% with a 6.7 at. % La concentration, without segregation of secondary phases. In addition, the substitution of La for Na gives rise to greater polarizability in the unit cell, which is related to the increase in the remnant polarization. Moreover, the decrease in the grain size allows for a reduction in the coercive field.

Both these effects result in improved ferroelectric and pyroelectric properties at low concentrations ($\leq 1.3\%$) of La. The 1.3% concentration yields the maximum in remnant polarization, as well as an appreciable reduction in the coercive field. The direct relationship between the remnant polarization and the pyroelectric coefficient shows that the pyroelectric response with the incorporation of La also yields the maximum pyroelectric response for a concentration of La at 1.3% and that the trend with La concentration is similar to that of P_r . This result is highly important because this approximate concentration of La facilitates the construction of efficient power light detectors, heat flux sensors useful in photopyroelectric techniques and in thin films, and infrared detectors.

In general, at La concentrations greater than or equal to 3.3%, the ferroelectric and pyroelectric properties of BNT are degraded due to the promotion of the cubic phase, which increases with higher La concentrations. Nevertheless, La concentrations around 6.7% are also important because they may facilitate the creation of BNT in the cubic stable phase, where its good dielectric properties may be useful in devices such as capacitors.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Stable solutions of a pure BNT system and doped with lanthanum using concentrations from 0 to 6.7 at. % were obtained using the sol-gel method and the acetic acid route; encapsulation of the samples in the sintering step was necessary to create bulk samples with high densification values of 94%–97%. An increase in the concentration of lanthanum suppresses grain growth, with the average grain size diminishing from 4.5 to 0.5 μm . The XRD results show that the addition of small concentrations (≤ 1.3 at. %) of lanthanum induces an increase in the volume of BNT cells and a phase transition from the rhombohedral to a non-ferroelectric phase when concentration increases up to 6.7 at. % La. The ferroelectric properties were improved by doping BNT with La (≤ 1.3 at. %); however, in samples with higher La concentrations, P_r drops quickly. The increase in lanthanum concentration leads to a change in transition temperature T_d to lower temperatures, from 220 to 71 $^\circ\text{C}$, while the dissipation factor $\tan(\delta)$ and maximum dielectric constant ϵ_{max} decrease from 0.05 to 0.035 and from 2600 to 830, respectively. The incorporation of La in low concentrations into BNT helps eliminate the defects and vacancies inherent in the processing of BNT. The compensation of these vacancies in random sites of Bi and Na maintains the rhombohedral structure and increases the remnant polarization as well as the pyroelectric response. In this low doping range, the coercive field is also reduced, accompanied by a decrease in grain size. A La concentration of 1.3% is the appropriate doping region for applications such as heat flux sensors and power radiation detectors due to its optimum pyroelectric response. At higher concentrations, a transition from the rhombohedral to cubic phase is promoted, with a consequent degradation in ferroelectric properties. Additional studies with concentrations of La around 6.7% would be enlightening because such concentrations would likely induce a complete transformation to a stable cubic structure whose dielectric properties would be of technological interest for capacitors.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this work.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available within the article.

REFERENCES

- 1 A. Ando and M. Kimura, "Resonator characteristics of bismuth layer structured ferroelectric materials," in *Lead-Free Piezoelectrics* (Shashank Priya and Sahn Nahm, 2013), pp. 373–403.
- 2 P. K. Panda and B. Sahoo, "PZT to lead free piezo ceramics: A review," *Ferroelectrics* **474**(1), 128–143 (2015).
- 3 P. K. Panda, "Review: Environmental friendly lead-free piezoelectric materials," *J. Mater. Sci.* **44**(19), 5049–5062 (2009).
- 4 G. A. Smolenskii, A. I. Agranovskaya, and V. A. Isupov, "New ferroelectrics of complex compound," *Sov. Phys. Solid State* **1**, 149–150 (1959).
- 5 P. Igor, P. P. Syrnikov, V. A. Isupov, V. M. Egorov, and N. V. Z. Zaitseva, "Peculiarities of phase transitions in sodium-bismuth titanate," *Ferroelectrics* **25**, 395–397 (1980).
- 6 K. Sakata and Y. Masuda, "Ferroelectric and antiferroelectric properties of $(\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5})\text{TiO}_3\text{-SrTiO}_3$ solid solution ceramics," *Ferroelectrics* **7**, 347–349 (1974).
- 7 T. Takenaka and K. Sakata, "Dielectric, piezoelectric and pyroelectric properties of $(\text{BiNa})_{1/2}\text{TiO}_3$ -based ceramics," *Ferroelectrics* **95**(1), 153–156 (1989).
- 8 H. D. Li, C. de Feng, and P. H. Xiang, "Electrical properties of La^{3+} -doped $(\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5})_{0.94}\text{Ba}_{0.06}\text{TiO}_3$ ceramics," *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys., Part 1* **42**(12), 7387–7391 (2003).
- 9 C. Xu, D. Lin, and K. W. Kwok, "Structure, electrical properties and depolarization temperature of $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})\text{TiO}_3\text{-BaTiO}_3$ lead-free piezoelectric ceramics," *Solid State Sci.* **10**(7), 934–940 (2008).
- 10 T. A. Duong *et al.*, "Dielectric and piezoelectric properties of $\text{Bi}_{1/2}\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{TiO}_3\text{-SrTiO}_3$ lead-free ceramics," *J. Electroceram.* **41**(1-4), 73–79 (2018).
- 11 A. B. Kouna, S. T. Zhang, W. Jo, T. Granzow, and J. Rödel, "Morphotropic phase boundary in $(1-x)\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3\text{-xK}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{NbO}_3$ lead-free piezoceramics," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **92**(22), 222902 (2008).
- 12 W. Zhao, H. P. Zhou, Y. K. Yan, and D. Liu, "Morphotropic phase boundary study of the BNT-BKT lead-free piezoelectric ceramics," *Key Eng. Mater.* **368-372**, 1908–1910 (2008).
- 13 D. Shan, Y. Qu, and J. Song, "Ionic doping effects on crystal structure and relaxation character in $\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$ ferroelectric ceramics," *J. Mater. Res.* **22**(3), 730–734 (2007).
- 14 F. Y. Lee, H. R. Jo, C. S. Lynch, and L. Pilon, "Pyroelectric energy conversion using PLZT ceramics and the ferroelectric-ergodic relaxor phase transition," *Smart Mater. Struct.* **22**(2), 025038 (2013).
- 15 C. A. Stanciu, M. Cernea, E. C. Secu, G. Aldica, P. Ganea, and R. Trusca, "Lanthanum influence on the structure, dielectric properties and luminescence of BaTiO_3 ceramics processed by spark plasma sintering technique," *J. Alloys Compd.* **706**, 538–545 (2017).
- 16 P. Eaksuwanchai, S. Jiansirisomboon, and A. Watcharaporn, "Effect of lanthanum additive on electrical and thermal properties of bismuth sodium titanate ceramics," *Integr. Ferroelectr.* **149**(1), 83–88 (2013).
- 17 P. Cousin and R. A. Ross, "Preparation of mixed oxides: A review," *Mater. Sci. Eng.: A* **130**, 119–125 (1990).

- ¹⁸Z. Xinle, M. Zhimei, X. Zuojiang, and C. Guang, "Preparation and characterization on nano-sized barium titanate powder doped with lanthanum by sol-gel process," *J. Rare Earths* **24**(1), 82–85 (2006).
- ¹⁹C. Y. Kim, T. Sekino, and K. Niihara, "Synthesis of bismuth sodium titanate nanosized powders by solution/sol-gel process," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **86**(9), 1464–1467 (2003).
- ²⁰K. M. Moya-Canul and J. M. Yáñez-Limón, "Study of $\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$ system doped with La^{3+} obtained by acetic acid route in sol-gel process," *Rev. Mex. Ing. Quim.* **19**(1), 335–343 (2020).
- ²¹A. K. Batra and M. D. Aggarwal, *Pyroelectric Materials: Infrared Detectors, Particle Accelerators and Energy Harvesters* (SPIE, Washington, 2013).
- ²²M. G. Rivera-Ruedas, J. R. Flores-Noria, F. J. G. Rodríguez, J. Muñoz-Saldaña, Y. Bucio-Hernández, M. G. Garnica-Romo, M. Avalos-Borja, and J. M. Yáñez-Limón, "PZT ferroelectric ceramics obtained by sol-gel method using 2-methoxyethanol route for pyroelectric sensors," *Mater. Res. Innovations* **13**(3), 375–378 (2009).
- ²³C. Montero-Tavera, M. D. Durruthy-Rodríguez, F. D. Cortés-Vega, and J. M. Yáñez-Limón, "Study of the structural, ferroelectric, dielectric, and pyroelectric properties of the $\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{NbO}_3$ system doped with Li^+ , La^{3+} , and Ti^{4+} ," *J. Adv. Ceram.* **9**(3), 329–338 (2020).
- ²⁴F. Remondiere, B. Malič, M. Kosec, and J.-P. Mercurio, "Study of the crystallization pathway of $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$ thin films obtained by chemical solution deposition," *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* **46**(2), 117–125 (2008).
- ²⁵J. Wei, Y. Pu, Y. Mao, and J. Wang, "Effects of BNT addition on the microstructure and PTC properties of La-doped BaTiO_3 -based PTCR ceramics," *Ferroelectrics* **403**(1), 91–96 (2010).
- ²⁶M. Hammer and M. J. Hoffmann, "Detailed x-ray diffraction analyses and correlation of microstructural and electromechanical properties of La-doped PZT ceramics," *J. Electroceram.* **2**, 75–84 (1998).
- ²⁷T. H. Dinh, H.-Y. Lee, C.-H. Yoon *et al.*, "Effect of lanthanum doping on the structural, ferroelectric, and strain properties of $\text{Bi}_{1/2}(\text{Na}_{0.82}\text{K}_{0.18})_{1/2}\text{TiO}_3$ lead-free ceramics," *J. Korean Phys. Soc.* **62**(7), 1004–1008 (2013).
- ²⁸Y. Yoneda, T. Nagamoto, T. Nakai, and M. Kobune, "Local structure analysis of $\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$, $\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.4}\text{Li}_{0.1}\text{TiO}_3$, and $0.95\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3\text{-}0.05\text{BaMn}_{1/3}\text{V}_2/3\text{O}_3$," *Trans. Mater. Res. Soc. Jpn.* **41**, 197–200 (2016).
- ²⁹A. Paul Blessington Selvadurai, V. Pazhivelu, B. K. Vasanth, C. Jagadeeshwaran, and R. Murugaraj, "Investigation of structural and optical spectroscopy of 5% Pr doped $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})\text{TiO}_3$ ferroelectric ceramics: Site depended study," *J. Mater. Sci.: Mater. Electron.* **26**(10), 7655–7665 (2015).
- ³⁰R. D. Shannon, "Revised effective ionic radii and systematic studies of interatomic distances in halides and chalcogenides," *Acta Crystallogr., Sect. A* **32**, 751–767 (1976).
- ³¹X. Liu, Y. Zhao, H. Hu, H. Du, and J. Shi, "Ionic conductive and dielectric properties of samarium isovalent doping in non-stoichiometric bismuth sodium titanate perovskite," *Ionics* **25**(6), 2729–2734 (2019).
- ³²F. Yang, M. Li, L. Li, P. Wu, E. Pradal-Velázquez, and D. C. Sinclair, "Defect chemistry and electrical properties of sodium bismuth titanate perovskite," *J. Mater. Chem. A* **6**(13), 5243–5254 (2018).
- ³³R. A. Young, *The Rietveld Method* (Oxford University Press, Oxford, United Kingdom, 1995).
- ³⁴K. A. Razak, C. J. Yip, and S. Sreekantan, "Synthesis of $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})\text{TiO}_3$ (BNT) and Pr doped BNT using the soft combustion technique and its properties," *J. Alloys Compd.* **509**(6), 2936–2941 (2011).
- ³⁵A. Herabut and A. Safari, "Processing and electromechanical properties of $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})_{(1-1.5x)}\text{La}_x\text{TiO}_3$ ceramics," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **80**(11), 2954–2958 (1997).
- ³⁶M. K. Niranjana, T. Karthik, S. Asthana, J. Pan, and U. V. Waghmare, "Theoretical and experimental investigation of Raman modes, ferroelectric and dielectric properties of relaxor $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$," *J. Appl. Phys.* **113**(19), 194106 (2013).
- ³⁷R. Selvamani, G. Singh, V. Sathe, V. S. Tiwari, and P. K. Gupta, "Dielectric, structural and Raman studies on $(\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3)_{(1-x)}(\text{BiCrO}_3)_x$ ceramic," *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **23**(5), 055901 (2011).
- ³⁸J. Petzelt, S. Kamba, J. Fábry, D. Noujni, V. Porokhonsky, A. Pashkin, I. Franke, K. Roleder, J. Suchanicz, R. Klein, and G. E. Kugel, "Infrared, Raman and high-frequency dielectric spectroscopy and the phase transitions in $\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{Bi}_{1/2}\text{TiO}_3$," *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **16**(15), 2719–2731 (2004).
- ³⁹J. Suchanicz, I. Jankowska-Sumara, and T. V. Kruszina, "Raman and infrared spectroscopy of $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3\text{-BaTiO}_3$ ceramics," *J. Electroceram.* **27**(2), 45–50 (2011).
- ⁴⁰S. N. Tripathy, K. K. Mishra, S. Sen, and D. K. Pradhan, "Dielectric and Raman spectroscopic studies of $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3\text{-BaSnO}_3$ ferroelectric system," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **97**(6), 1846–1854 (2014).
- ⁴¹S. Shanmuga Sundari, B. Kumar, and R. Dhanasekaran, "Synthesis, dielectric and relaxation behavior of lead free NBT–BT ceramics," *Ceram. Int.* **39**(1), 555–561 (2013).
- ⁴²K. K. Mishra, V. Sivasubramanian, R. M. Sarguna, T. R. Ravindran, and A. K. Arora, "Phonons in La-substituted $\text{BiFeO}_3\text{-PbTiO}_3$," *AIP Conf. Proc.* **1313**, 174–176 (2010).
- ⁴³J. Shi, H. Fan, X. Liu, and A. J. Bell, "Large electrostrictive strain in $(\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})\text{TiO}_3\text{-BaTiO}_3\text{-(Sr}_{0.7}\text{Bi}_{0.2})\text{TiO}_3$ solid solutions," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **97**(3), 848–853 (2014).
- ⁴⁴V. D. N. Tran, A. Ullah, T. H. Dinh, and J.-S. Lee, "Effect of lanthanum doping on ferroelectric and strain properties of $0.96\text{Bi}_{1/2}(\text{Na}_{0.84}\text{K}_{0.16})_{1/2}\text{TiO}_3\text{-}0.04\text{SrTiO}_3$ lead-free ceramics," *J. Electron. Mater.* **45**(5), 2639–2643 (2016).
- ⁴⁵Y. Watanabe, Y. Hiruma, H. Nagata, and T. Takenaka, "Electrical properties and phase transition temperatures of lanthanoid substituted $(\text{Bi}_{1/2}\text{Na}_{1/2})\text{TiO}_3$ ceramics," *Ferroelectrics* **358**(1), 139–143 (2007).
- ⁴⁶J. Y. Yi, J. K. Lee, and K. S. Hong, "Dependence of the microstructure and the electrical properties of lanthanum-substituted $(\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{Bi}_{1/2})\text{TiO}_3$ on cation vacancies," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **85**(12), 3004–3010 (2002).
- ⁴⁷J.-K. Lee, J. Y. Yi, and K. S. Hong, "Dependence of incommensurate phase formation on vacancy type in La-doped $(\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{Ba}_{1/2})\text{TiO}_3$," *J. Appl. Phys.* **96**(2), 1174–1177 (2004).
- ⁴⁸J. Y. Yi, J.-K. Lee, and K. S. Hong, "The role of cation vacancies on microstructure and piezoelectricity of lanthanum-substituted $(\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{Bi}_{1/2})\text{TiO}_3$ ceramics," *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys., Part 1* **43**(9A), 6188–6192 (2004).
- ⁴⁹J. S. Kim, S. B. Kim, and B. C. Choi, "Effect of La doping on the dielectric and the ferroelectric properties of lead-free $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$ (NBT) ferroelectric ceramics," *J. Korean Phys. Soc.* **54**(92), 911–915 (2009).
- ⁵⁰R. D. Shannon, "Dielectric polarizabilities of ions in oxides and fluorides," *J. Appl. Phys.* **73**(1), 348–366 (1993).
- ⁵¹L. Jin, F. Li, and S. Zhang, "Decoding the fingerprint of ferroelectric loops: Comprehension of the material properties and structures," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **97**(1), 1–27 (2014).